

Sowden and Fischer prepared D-arabinose and D-ribose from D-erythrose³, and L-glucose and L-mannose from L-arabinose⁴. In this communication D-mannose was condensed with nitromethane in the presence of sodium methoxide to give 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol in high yield. The carbohydrate nitroalcohol was then subjected to the Nef reaction with 18 N sulphuric acid. As a result a pure product of D-glycero-D-galactoheptose was obtained in high yield.

Experimental

1-Nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol: In the first step, D-mannose (4 g) in absolute methanol (10 ml) and of nitromethane (16 ml) was added to sodium (1 g) in absolute methanol (18 ml). The resulting mixture was shaken for 5 h. The product was then cooled to -20° . It was filtered and the precipitate was washed first with methanol and then with ether. It was dissolved in ice-water and then passed through a cation-exchange column. The effluent was concentrated under reduced pressure when crystals of 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol separated out (2.6 g, 68%), m.p. 198° (Found: C, 35.10; H, 5.41; N, 5.82. Calcd. C, 35.14; H, 5.43; N, 5.85%); $[\alpha]_D +24^{\circ}$.

Conversion of 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol to D-glycero-D-galactoheptose: 1-Nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol (0.5 g) was dissolved in 1 N sodium hydroxide (2 ml) and the mixture was then added to 18 N sulphuric acid (4 ml) with stirring. Heating facilitated the reaction. It was heated for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered and passed through three ion-exchange columns. The resulting solution was concentrated when D-glycero-D-galactoheptose was obtained (0.44 g, 88%), m.p. $135-136^{\circ}$ (Found: C, 40.2, H, 6.63. Calcd. C, 40.0; H, 6.66%); $[\alpha]_D +68^{\circ}$. It was dissolved in water and then acidified with acetic acid. The solution was treated with phenylhydrazine in 50% acetic acid when D-glycero-D-galactoheptose phenylhydrazone precipitated out on standing, m.p. 196° .

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Biflavonoids from Leaves of *Cunninghamia lanceolata* Hook. f.

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THE genus *Cunninghamia* (Family, Taxodiaceae) consists of only two species, evergreen conifers found in China, of which *Cunninghamia lanceolata*

Hook. f. (Syn. *C. sinensis* R. Br.) is grown in India as an ornamental plant. The wood is of commercial value as being used for the manufacture of paper pulp¹.

Both the species, *Cunninghamia lanceolata* Hook. f. and *C. lanceolata* Var², were examined earlier, and found to contain hinokiflavone and kayaflavone, alongwith sequoiaflavone or sotetsuflavone. The present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of eight flavonoid pigments from the leaf extracts of *Cunninghamia lanceolata* Hook. f. Robustaflavone is being reported for the first time in the genus *Cunninghamia* and its presence in the species may serve as a useful taxonomic marker.

The phenolic extractives of powdered leaves by solvent fractionation and column chromatography (Si-gel) followed by preparative tlc yielded five flavonoid fractions (+ve shinoda test)⁴ labelled as CLI-CLV. CLI on methylation followed by tlc examination and characteristic fluorescence in uv light^{5,6} was found to be the mixture of amentoflavone and robustaflavone. The methylated product was subjected to preparative tlc to give CLI MI and CLI MII. CLI MI, m.p. 226° , Rf 0.41, mol. wt. 622 (*M*) was characterised as amentoflavone hexamethyl ether (**1e**) by comparison with authentic sample (m.p., Rf values, fluorescence in uv light and nmr data)^{5,7,8}, CLI MII, m.p. 308° , Rf 0.51, mol. wt. 622 (*M*) was found identical with authentic sample of robustaflavone hexamethyl ether (**2b**) (m.p., Rf values, fluorescence in uv light and nmr data)^{9,10}. CLII was found on complete methylation to be a mixture of hinokiflavone and mono-*o*-methylamentoflavone on tlc (Rf values and fluorescence in uv light)⁵. CLII was, therefore, subjected to CCD separation between ethylmethyl ketone and borate buffer (pH 9.8) to give CLII X and CLII Y. CLII X was characterised as sequoiaflavone (**1b**) by nmr studies of its acetate and methyl ether and also by comparison with authentic sample⁹. CLII Y was identified with hinokiflavone (**3a**) by comparison with authentic samples (m.p., Rf values, and nmr data of acetate and methyl ether)¹⁰. CLIII and its complete methyl ether CLIII M showed on tlc examination to be mono-*o*-methylhinokiflavone. On acetylation, it gave an acetate CLIIIA, m.p. $213-214^{\circ}$, which was analysed for isocryptomerin tetraacetate by nmr spectral studies¹¹. CLIII was thus assigned the structure as isocryptomerin (**3b**). Tlc examination of CLIV and its complete methyl ether showed it to be a mixture of di-*o*-methylamentoflavone and apigenin^{5,12}. CLIV on CCD separation yielded CLIV X and CLIV Y which were characterised as I-7, II-7-di-*o*-methylamentoflavone (**1c**) and apigenin (**4a**), respectively by direct comparison of nmr data of their acetates with those of the authentic samples^{13,14}. Tlc examination of CLV and its methyl ether showed it to be tri-*o*-methylamentoflavone. It was identified as kayaflavone (**1d**) by comparison of nmr data of its acetate with that of the authentic sample¹⁵.

(1)

- a $R=R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$
 b $R=R_2=R_3=R_4=H, R_1=Me$
 c $R=R_2=R_3=H, R_1=R_4=Me$
 d $R=R_1=H, R_2=R_3=R_4=Me$
 e $R=R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=Me$

(2)

- a $R=H$
 b $R=Me$

(3)

- a $R=R_1=H$
 b $R=H, R_1=Me$
 c $R=R_1=Me$

(4)

- a $R=H$
 b $R=Me$

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Tlc analysis was performed on silica gel-G (B.D.H.) in benzene-pyridine-formic acid (BPF) (36 : 9 : 5). Nmr spectra were recorded in $CDCl_3$ solution on a JEOLPS-100 instrument with TMS as an internal standard.

Extraction: Dried and powdered leaves (2.5 kg) collected from Darjeeling, West Bengal, India, after exhaustive extraction with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) were treated several times with boiling acetone. The combined acetone extracts on removal of the solvent gave a dark viscous mass which was then treated successively with petroleum ether, benzene, chloroform and water. The residue left was dissolved in ethanol and dried under reduced pressure to give a dark brown mass (5 g) which responded to the usual colour tests for flavonoids.

Chromatographic separation: The dark brown mass (5 g) was adsorbed on Si-gel (10 g) in dry acetone (20 ml) and transferred to a column of Si-gel (200 g) made up with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). Elution was performed with organic solvents in increasing order of polarity. Fractions eluted with EtOAc and EtOAc-acetone (1 : 1) gave positive tests for flavonoids. These were combined and concentrated to give yellowish brown solid (2.0 g) which was separated by preparative tlc into five fractions labelled as CLI (Rf 0.17, 150 mg), CLII (Rf 0.37, 300 mg), CLIII (Rf 0.50, 200 mg), CLIV (Rf 0.55, 200 mg) and CLV (Rf 0.62, 80 mg).

Amentoflavone (1a) and robustaflavone (2a): Fraction CLI (120 mg) on methylation with Me_2SO_4 (1 ml) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (3 g) in dry acetone (300 ml) by refluxing on a water-bath for 12 h and tlc examination gave two methyl ethers corresponding to hexamethylethers of amentoflavone and robustaflavone. The methyl ethers were separated by

preparative tlc to give CLI MI (50 mg) and CLI MII (40 mg). CLI MI crystallised from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH as colourless needles of amentoflavone hexamethyl ether (1e), Rf 0.41, m.p. 226°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 267, 369 nm; mol.wt. 622 (M). CLI MII on crystallisation from EtOAc yielded colourless cubes of robustaflavone hexamethyl ether (2b), Rf 0.51, m.p. 308°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 268, 365 nm, mol. wt. 622 (M).

Sequoiaflavone (1b) and hinokiflavone (3a): CLII (60 mg) was methylated with Me_2SO_4 (0.5 ml) and fused K_2CO_3 (2 g) in boiling dry acetone for 10 h. After complete methylation, the product showed two spots on tlc corresponding to permethyl ethers of amentoflavone and hinokiflavone. Preparative tlc yielded both components, one colourless needles of amentoflavone hexamethyl ether by crystallisation from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH (20 mg), m.p. 226°, Rf. 0.41, showed no m.p. depression on admixture with our sample (CLI MI). The other component gave colourless cubes (20 mg) of penta-O-methylhinokiflavone (3a-methyl ether) on crystallisation from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH, m.p. 260-262°, Rf 0.51. CLII (220 mg) was subjected to counter-current distribution between $MeCOEt$ (10 ml) and borate buffer (pH 9.8, 10 ml). After 60 transfers it was separated into two components, CLII X and CLII Y. CLII X obtained from tubes 3-30 gave yellow crystals (100 mg) of sequoiaflavone (1b) by crystallisation from MeOH, m.p. > 300°, mol. wt. 552 (M). The pigment (60 mg) was acetylated with Ac_2O (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) by heating for 2 h. The product on usual work up and crystallisation from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH yielded colourless needles of sequoiaflavone pentaacetate (1b-acetate) (35 mg), m.p. 194-196°, mol. wt. 762 (M). CLII Y (tubes 35-60) was crystallised from MeOH-pyridine to give yellow prisms of hinokiflavone (3a) (60 mg), m.p. > 300°. It was acetylated from Ac_2O and pyridine and crystallised from EtOAc to give colourless needles of hinokiflavone pentaacetate (3a-acetate) (45 mg), m.p. 240°.

Isocryptomerin (3b): CLIII (50 mg) was methylated as described to give a methylether CLIIIM (35 mg), Rf 0.51, which was found identical with penta-O-methylhinokiflavone (3a-methyl ether). CLIII (70 mg) was acetylated with Ac_2O and pyridine to give an acetate which on crystallisation from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH yielded colourless needles of isocryptomerin tetraacetate (3b-acetate) (50 mg), m.p. 211-213°.

I-7, II-7-Di-O-methylamentoflavone (1c) and apigenin (4a): CLIV (150 mg) was subjected to CCD separation as in CLII and yielded CLIV X (tubes 1-30, 60 mg) and CLIV Y (tubes 35-55, 50 mg). CLIV X on crystallisation from EtOAc gave yellow crystals of I-7, II-7-di-O-methylamentoflavone (1c) (55 mg), m.p. 300°. On acetylation and crystallisation from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH, it yielded colourless needles of I-7, II-7-di-O-methylamentoflavone tetraacetate (1c-acetate) (40 mg), mol. wt. 734 (M). CLIV Y was crystallised from EtOAc to give yellow crystals of apigenin (4a) (45 mg); λ_{max} (EtOH) 268, 341 nm. On acetylation and crystallisation, it yielded colour-

less cubes of apigenin triacetate (4a-acetate) (35 mg), m.p. 182°, mol. wt. 396 (M).

Kayaflavone (1d): CLV (50 mg) was acetylated with Ac₂O and pyridine and the product was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH to give colourless cubes of kayaflavone triacetate (1d-acetate) (30 mg), m.p. 190-192°, mol. wt. 706 (M).

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Triterpenoids and Flavonoids from the

Leaves of *Pongamia glabra* Vent.

Demethylation Studies on 5-Methoxyfuranoflavones

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PONGAMIA glabra Vent. (Fam. Leguminosae) is well-known for producing furano-, pyrano- and simple flavonoids¹. Our recent investigation^{1,2} on the flowers of this plant led to the isolation of a number

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of flavonoids along with two triterpenoids, cycloart-23-ene-3 β , 25-diol and friedelin, and one phenylalanine derived dipeptide aurantiamide acetate. No triterpenoid or dipeptide was previously isolated from this plant although Mahey *et al.*³ reported the possibility of occurrence of terpenoids in the leaves. The leaves of *P. glabra* were, therefore, reinvestigated particularly with a view to study their non-flavonoid constituents.

In this reinvestigation, four triterpenoids, cycloart-23-ene-3 β , 25-diol, friedelin, lupeol and lupenone, four furanoflavones, karanjin, 5-methoxyfuran(4'',5''-8,7)flavone (1), pongapin and 3'-methoxypongapin, one chromenoflavone pongachromene, one simple flavone kanugin, and β -sitosterol have been isolated. Pongapin (m.p. 190°), 3'-methoxypongapin (m.p. 182°), and pongachromene (m.p. 195°) have been characterised from their uv, ir and ¹H nmr spectral features and the other compounds by direct comparison with the authentic samples^{1,3,4}.

Dried and powdered leaves (1 kg) of *P. glabra* were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with chloroform for 40 h. The concentrate of the extract (38 g) was chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarities. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE-1

Eluent	Compound isolated	Amount mg
Light petrol-EtOAc		
97:3	Lupenone	16
97:3	Friedelin	10
95:5	Lupeol	106
9:1	β -Sitosterol	210
9:1	Karanjin	182
85:15	Pongapin	10
85:15	Pongachromene	22
4:1	3'-Methoxypongapin	18
4:1	Kanugin	108
4:1	Cycloart-23-ene-3 β , 25-diol	4
2:1	5-Methoxyfuran(4'',5''-8,7)flavone (1)	82

In our earlier papers we reported^{1,5} that the ¹H and ¹³C nmr signals for the OCH₃ group of 5-methoxyfuran(4'',5''-8,7)flavone (1) appeared at higher fields than those of its linear isomer pinnatin (2). The ¹H nmr signal for the chelated OH of pongaglabol (3) also appeared¹ at a higher field than that of 5-hydroxyfuran(4'',5''-6,7)flavone (4). These differences were thought to be due to the different mode of fusion of the furano moiety to the flavone nucleus (8,7 in 1 and 3 and 6,7 in 2 and 4) effecting different extent of electron transfer from the C-5 OCH₃ or OH to the flavone carbonyl site. Here we report the observed differences in demethylation of the 5-methoxyfuranoflavones, 1 and 2, under mild demethylating conditions, (i) refluxing with 6 N ethanolic HCl⁶ and (ii) treatment with dry AlCl₃ at room temperature⁷, generally